

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

To Cite:

Imran, A., Khan, S. Khan, M. A. Khalid, U. Mehmood, A. Environmental life cycle assessment of cement produced at Hattar Industrial Estate, Haripur. *IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal* 2023; Vol 1, Issue 1, pp. 20-44.

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Peer-Review History

Received: 24th October 2023

Reviewed & Revised: 08/November/2023 to 28/November/2023

Accepted: 29th November 2023

Published: 30th November 2023

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

ISSNxxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/integratemind-journal>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

Human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

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Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of Cement Produced at Hattar Industrial Estate, Haripur

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ABSTRACT

Finding out the impacts on environment was the main goal of this research study during the cement manufacturing process, and to give some suggestions to minimize the effects on the environment during manufacturing process of cement. The industry's administration is responsible for maintenance and conservation of the green spaces within and surrounding the industry. The cement industry must be dedicated to comprehending the effects of its output. Therefore, it must find a way to cut back on substances that have a significant negative influence on the environment. Exponential growth of industrialization and urbanization has led to the issues of pollution. The study's main objective is to inquire into the emission inventory repercussions of toxic substances on soil, water, and air for 1 cement bag produced by cement industry in Hattar Industrial Estate Haripur during 2021-2022. Most of the emissions were from the slate, clay, limestone and limestone. The study examines how outputs and inputs for resources, such as raw materials, slate, limestone, clay and limestone affects the environment. The research evaluates outputs and inputs for resources, such as raw materials, affect the environment. The primary material slate, limestone, clay and limestone accounted for the vast majority of environmental impact categories ' largest contributions, whereas primary materials for a cement manufacture made a key contribution to abiotic depletion, global warming (GWP100), eutrophication potential, photochemical oxidation, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, and marine aquatic eco toxicity impacts

Keywords: Cement, abiotic depletion, global warming potential, eutrophication potential, photochemical oxidation, ozone layer depletion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Concern for environmental conservation and infrastructure associated with environmental issues have got more attention recently, and are now a major factor in the creation of economic and social policies. Large number of these attempts have emphasized on cutting down greenhouse gas exhalation, particularly carbon dioxide (CO₂), which is in charge of retaining heat in the atmosphere. The atmospheric concentration of carbon dioxide for the first time ever hit the momentous 400 part per million-mile stone in year 2015, as stated by world meteorological Organization Annual Greenhouse Gas Bulletin in the year 2016.

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The World Business Council for Sustainable Development and the IEA looked specifically into the environmental effects of the cement industry in 2009 because cement ranks as the second most used substance following water and its manufacturing throughout the globe is allied with considerable CO₂ discharge, stated by numerous conducted research studies. Cement, in the production of hydraulic concrete is employed as a binder (Cao et al., 2016; Feiz et al., 2015; Stafford et al., 2016). Indeed, it is believed that this sector accounts of producing around 5% of the world's CO₂ emissions caused by humans today (Summerbell et al., 2016). Clinker, a solid used to build cement, is produced by burning a variety of materials, including limestone, clay, and other elements that resemble clay, in rotating kilns at 1400 C. Afterwards, cement is made by mixing clinker with gypsum and other ingredients (Rossetti, 2007). Both chemical and physical greenhouse emissions are produced during the production of cement: in the midst of limestone heating generates CO₂ chemically, the heating of the kiln by fossil fuels also generates CO₂ physically. The equation is used to determine the chemical emissions caused by the calcination of raw materials:

Where CaCO₃ is calcium carbonate, CaO indicates for calcium oxide, while CO₂(g) represents carbon dioxide. Despite the knowledge that these emissions cannot be reduced, physical emissions can be decreased by using alternative energy sources or implementing energy-efficient techniques. Like in the case of carbon profile of the cement industry may be immediately impacted by using alternative energy sources such as waste products or biomass (Supino et al., 2016). The results of a cement industry life cycle assessment (LCA) will be useful to figure out the impacts on environment of cement manufacturing (Moretti et al., 2014), in order to correlate with the environmental effects of various construction materials (Moretti et al., 2013, 2016, 2017) and/or to evaluate particular environmental results of projects built with such materials (Loprencipe & Cantisani, 2015).

1.1 Description of the Cement Production Process

In order to form the clinker composition, the fuel ash is added together with other fundamental components like crushing limestone along with silicon, aluminum, and iron oxides before milling the resulting raw meal into cement. This unprocessed material is mixed in mixing silos before being pre-heated in the system, which separates carbonate into calcium oxide and carbon dioxide. After that, the meal is heated in the kiln. Calcium silicates and aluminates are produced when calcium oxide and other elements react at a temperature of around 1500 °C. To maintain a high enough temperature in the chemical's burning zone, primary fuel is used. An assemblage composed of C₃S, C₂S, C₃A, and C₄AF forms when the clinker cools to a temperature below the solidus point. The clinker will subsequently be mixed with gypsum, limestone and ashes to produce cement, a finer product (Habert, 2013).

I. Limestone Quarrying and Crushing:

Calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) is obtained from quarries, which are frequently situated adjacent to the cement factory, and found naturally calcareous formations including limestone, marl, or chalk. If more iron oxide (Fe₂O₃), alumina (Al₂O₃) and silica (SiO₂) are needed to adjust the chemical makeup of the raw mixed to the process and for the final product, very little volumes of "corrective" materials such as iron ore, bauxite, shale, clay, or sand are added.

II. Raw Mill:

Usually grinding process affects the production of cement. First, as the raw mix, it becomes more uniform and finer, the clinker reactions quicken. As the kiln is more steady and uses less energy as a result, the clinker becomes less varied and more constant. The second effect is related to the cement's fineness, which improves the finished product's mechanical qualities.

III. Blending and Storing Silo:

Effective blending and homogenization of the raw materials is required to lessen the naturally accruing chemical variance across the numerous raw materials, silos are used for this.

IV. Pre Heater & Kiln:

In a preheater, where unprocessed meal is forced through a series of vertical cyclones, hot, whirling exhaust gases from a kiln moving in the opposite direction come into contact with the raw meal. Pre-heating of the raw meals occurs in these cyclones before sliding into the kiln by recovering thermal energy from the hot flue gases. A kiln may have contained up to six based on the moisture content, of raw materials.

V. Cooler:

The system loses the least amount of energy when the hot clinker (1500 °C) from the kiln slides onto a cooling grate and is tempered by entering combustion air to 170 °C (Zeman, 2009).

VI. Cement Mill:

This is the concluding stage in the process of making cement. In this stage, the cement clinker and additives are grinded in a cement mill. To achieve the setting time, all type of cements contains 4-5 percentage of gypsum. However, many modern companies now use more reliable technology like roller presses and vertical mills, ball mills etc. Ball mills have historically been the preferred

method of grinding. Ball mills, vertical roller mills, high pressure roller presses, and horizontal roller press mills are four main types of grinding systems for raw materials. Despite a decline in its utilization in new plant construction, ball mills are still utilized for grinding clinker. A vertical roller mill consumes around 40% less energy than a conventional ball mill. Finish grinding is done in vertical mills with inbuilt separators that have a 350 ton per hour mill capacity. In many different systems, high-pressure roller presses (HPRP) are used as a single stage grinding procedure to finish grinding in conjunction with ball mills for primary grinding and semi-final grinding. The utilization of horizontal roller press mills as a single stage grinding procedure is practical. Throughout rates are barely 120 tons per hour despite energy efficiency of 50% relative to ball mills and 20% relative to vertical mills (Madloul et al., 2011).

1.2 Lifecycle Assessment

Life cycle assessment has proven to be a beneficial way for analyzing the impact of cement manufacturing in its industrial stage in order to develop more environmental friendly cement and concrete products and manufacturing processes (Gäbel et al., 2004; Josa et al., 2004; Marceau et al., 2006 a; Navia et al., 2006). For analyzing the harmful impacts of clinker production and the supply chains that are connected to it, lifecycle assessment can be proven to be useful (Boesch & Hellweg, 2010).

1.2.1. Stages of Lifecycle Assessment:

I. Goal and Scope Definition

Each LCA's main objective component is of vital importance. It defines the following, more specific characteristics in addition to the purpose for carrying out a certain research study, its objectives, depth, the system or systems to be worked upon, and the standards:

- System limitations (geographic, technical and time)
- Practical unit (reference function)
- The type of impact evaluation and valuation; rules and assumptions (e.g. data, allocation rules for coproducts and open-loop recycling, aggregate);
- The target group(s) for the study (internal, marketing, general public, politics)

II. Inventory Analysis:

Inventory analysis is the core, most thorough, LCA stage. It is widely recognized and has been in use ever since. The main message of the inventory is that all actions that go into producing a single functional unit must be examined in light of the following factors: the raw material extraction, the manufacturing of intermediate products, the creation of the finalized product or services, the usage step leading finally to the disposal of wastage. Energy, transportation, and ancillary items are all considered inputs. Examples of outputs include coproducts, emissions released to air, water, soil, solid wastes, and heat waste.

III. Impact Assessment (LCIA)

In order to enhance the products, benchmarking, saving energy, as well as lowering emissions, a standalone Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) analysis with goals definition and scope might be helpful. However, the LCI is insufficient for comparing product system evaluations. A rigorous impact evaluation must be carried out for this crucial application and for a greater comprehension of the systems under investigation.

IV. Interpretation (Improvement Assessment)

In the course of the ISO standardization work, a new component of LCA called interpretation was introduced (ISO 14043). It attempts to offer a critical assessment of the complete LCA, rather than just the impact assessment, and connects the LCA with applications that aren't addressed by the LCA employing numerical methods (sensitivity analysis, dominance analysis).

1.3 Research Objectives

The following are the research objectives of the study, i.e.,

- To analyze the key environmental issues related to the production process of cement.
- To analyze that how energy and different raw material inputs are associated with different environmental burdens and subsequent environmental release thereof.
- To analyze the alternate scenarios or recommendations to reduce the environmental burden during the production process.

1.4 Motivation

The demand for building materials has risen as a result of rapid urbanization. The cement business is a major cause of environmental deterioration, particularly during manufacturing when tons of hazardous gases and dust are released into the air, which having adverse impact on environment. The use of energy and the loss of natural resources are further issues. Therefore,

research on these effects and how they affect the ecosystem is required. As in concern to cement industries very limited amount of researches has been carried out on LCA of milling process and water footprint analysis of cement industries. After identifying the phases of these processes that are upstream and core, the main goal of this study was to evaluate the impact on the environment of the cement industry. LCA of cement businesses is vital if we are to reduce environmental costs and offer substitutes for the issues associated with cement manufacture. Data for the study was collected through primary source. Published literature and internal record of the mills was used to gain information regarding all the key stages of cement production as well as details about production capacity of cement mills, electricity usage during whole milling process, fossil fuels consumption (i.e. stationary and mobile sources), transportation of products inside the mill and amount of waste generated during this process.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following literature review helps to build the foundation to assess the lifecycle assessment of cement industry worldwide. Gursel (2014) completed investigation on cement's life cycle assessment in which he explained that the development business fundamentally affects the climate, consuming roughly 40% of overall regular assets in this way prompting ecological contamination and organic harms from the extraction exercises of these assets. Gan et al. (2017) analysis of the embedded carbon in high-rise structures in comparison to several design criteria in 2017 according to which it is understood that the building industry uses energy to a degree that accounts for around 40% of global GHG emissions. Another study conducted by Damtoft et al. (2008) and Nagrockienė et al. (2017) concluded that concrete has been broadly utilized as a significant structure material because of its promptly open constituents and its unmistakable properties, like ease of use, strength and solidness. Devi et al. (2017) analyzed that concrete, a significant part of cement, is likewise the most broadly man-made material for structures and framework on the planet. Its creation and utilization is fairly connected with the financial development of a specific region, and the concrete business likewise sets out specific work open doors and gives monetary advantages to its connected areas. Morsali (2016) evaluates the emissions from Portland cement production applying the inventory and procedure of life cycle assessment and concluded that as it may, being an energy- and asset concentrated industry, concrete assembling is related with different ecological issues, for example, a dangerous atmospheric deviation, air contamination, fermentation, asset consumption and land use change. Ali et al. (2011) argued that cement industrial sector alone produces about 7 percent of the world's anthropogenic carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and utilizes close to 12 to 15 percent of all industrial energy. In the calcination process, almost half of the CO₂ required to make cement is emitted, which decarbonizes limestone, and the other half is used to produce energy from sources like fossil fuels and electricity (Huntzinger & Eatmon 2009). 4.1 billion tons of cement were generated worldwide in 2017. Increasing cement output will result in increased CO₂ emissions if nothing is done. Marceau et al. (2006 b) and Tang et al. (2018) did a thorough study on the emissions from cement industry which summarizes that the concrete business is a significant supporter of discharges of residue/particulate matter (PM), sulfur oxides (SO_x), nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and carbon monoxide (CO) as well as weighty metals.

These discharges are falling apart air quality as well as harming people's health. Releases have neighborhood and globally climate influence bringing about an Earth-wide temperature boost, ozone consumption, corrosive downpour, biodiversity misfortune, diminished crop efficiency and so forth. Pollution prevention and abatement handbook 1998, stated that scientific evidences show that air pollution from burning non-renewable energy sources results in a variety of health effects, including sensitivity to death. The repercussions of a few examinations showed that these emanations are unfavorably impacting the wellbeing of humans in different ways, as irritation in eyes, sicknesses of respiratory tracts like tuberculosis, chest distress, constant bronchitis, asthma assaults, cardio vascular illness and, surprisingly, sudden passing. The group of nitrogen oxides, which includes nitrogen dioxide, nitric acid, nitrous oxide, nitrates, and nitric oxide, accounts for a variation of human health and environmental impacts. As of Sulphur dioxide, NO_x reacts with water and other mixes to produce various acidic mixtures. When these acidic mixes reach the earth's surface, they can contaminate lakes and streams and alter the water composition of numerous water bodies. It is difficult for certain fish and other sea-going organisms to survive, develop, and replicate fermentation (low pH) and the synthetic alterations it causes. Additionally, corrosive rain can impair rural areas by directly destroying plant tissues (Kunt & Özkan, 2023). A greenhouse gas that damages ozone, nitrous oxide builds up in the atmosphere together with other nursery gases, slowly raising global temperatures. A global temperature rise and environmental impact will result from this. Ground-level ozone is created when NO_x and unstable natural mixes react in the air in the presence of daylight to form brown haze in urban and rural areas. Inhaling this ground-level ozone can result in respiratory illnesses and other health problems (Soares & Silva, 2022). Nitrogen dioxide affects bodily functions including breathing difficulties, chronic lung diseases like chronic irritation, and permanent primary lung alterations, which when repeated in an open environment can cause premature lung ageing and other respiratory illnesses.

The main negative effects of VOCs include damage, potential contribution to brown haze through photochemical climatic reactions, and potential contribution to the "nursery impact" and resulting hazardous atmospheric deviation (Woodard). There is

evidence linking dust discharges to respiratory conditions like tuberculosis. The focus on low-energy concretes, the utilization of waste in the production of concrete, and the resulting reduction in CO₂ emissions are recent developments in the field of concrete production. A crucial relationship is the evaluation of the direct impact on the climate. Nearly only CO₂ is projected to have an impact on Earth's global temperature, whereas Sox (34 percent), NH₃ (30 percent), N₂O (17 percent), SO₂ (13 percent), and NO_x are mostly responsible for fermentation (6 percent) Its implications for marine ecosystem poisoning are mostly linked to the emission of Fluorine and its inorganic mixes (54%) barite and barium (34%), as well as several heavy metals like vanadium (3 percent). The variation of three types of emissions (Dust, NO_x, and SO₂) from 1993 to 1999 in six different cement plants was examined by Von Bahr and co-authors (Von Bahr et al., 2003). They demonstrate both the gradual development of procedures and the significant variation amongst cement plants.

The cement industry can reduce production waste through the use of appropriate technology and computational modelling, while also abiding by environmental protection laws, regulating air quality, and investigating how computer modelling can be used for the classification, quantification, and control of particulate matter, as well as how efficient energy use can help to achieve these goals. The two primary greenhouse gases that are generated during the production of cement are carbon dioxide and nitrogen oxide. Coal, which is the main thermal fuel used in combustion, plays a significant role in the production of these GHG. How big of an influence the cement manufacturing process has depends on the type of fuel used, the needs for the raw materials, and the production method used. In the united states, private and business structures are liable for around 74% power use and 39% of yearly essential energy use starting around 2006, this rate is supposed to develop. (Vieira & Horvath, 2008) conducted a study on assessing the end of life impacts of building in 2008 in which they concluded that, globally, 40% of anthropogenic GHG emanations and 40% of unrefined components are credited to structures. Another discursive study on Portland cement was conducted by (Nigri et al., 2010) which concluded that cement production process can produce nearby natural effects, for example, commotion, decreased air quality, changes in the neighborhood environment because of extraction of unrefined components like earth, limestone, and others. Locally it can make corrosive downpour due emanation of sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) among others. Currently the consuming of petroleum products like oil, coal and flammable gas might cause environment changes around the world. As indicated by the International Energy Agency (IEA) concrete creation produces a worldwide typical CO₂ discharge of 0.81 kg.kg⁻¹ of concrete delivered. By and large, around one ton of cement is delivered every year for all people all over the planet. It is assessed that around 5% of worldwide CO₂ discharges come from the production of concrete. Other than the age of CO₂ during the time spent assembling concrete, are delivered huge number of lots of waste (particulate matter from the concrete oven) every year that add to contamination and respiratory wellbeing gambles. The calcination cycle of getting CaO from CaCO₃ creates CO₂ and adds to about a portion of the CO₂ discharged, while the rest comes from energy utilization during the creation interaction.

Because of the qualities of the mechanical cycle and the physicochemical and toxicological properties of natural substances and data sources utilized in the concrete assembling, clinker and concrete itself, the concrete plants make a gamble the wellbeing of laborers, general wellbeing and the climate. They are basically connected with openness to particulate matter that saturates the whole chain of creation and discharges of poisons that happen persistently and that even in little focuses, portraying the ongoing gamble. It very well may be seen in Table 1 that all phases of concrete assembling produce effects on the climate. It is additionally noticed that a large part of the energy utilized in the process centers around the step of utilizing ovens and the resulting discharge of particulate matter into air. During the natural substance extraction ecological effects emerge as the evacuation of vegetation for the nearby mining action and a potential tainting of groundwater because of particulate matter created in the extraction, among others. During the devastating, crushing and blending, as well as essentially the whole assembling process is the outflow of particulate matter and unpredictable substances to the work area and into the air can cause a few medical conditions. In the phase of utilizing the oven or combination step is consuming more energy and accordingly has the best ecological effect. This is expected not exclusively to the consuming of petroleum product that discharges weighty metals as well as CO₂ and SO₂, yet in addition by the calcination cycle.

Also little size strong particles are produced to the climate (concrete furnace dust). Because of its scathing nature residue might make disturbance skin, eyes, and create respiratory issues. After the mixing up, the discharge of particulate matter in the blending, crushing, bundling and delivery steps has likewise to be considered. The stage likewise gives the utilization of strong waste issue. Taking into account the existence of the concrete in the development business (or in the structure life), as a general rule, there are no particulate emanations, ozone depleting substances or toxins. Be that as it may, its removal as trash is the main issue. With the ascent in urban communities and a decreased helpful existence of structures, the age of flotsam and jetsam has become progressively bigger and frequently perplexing, since it has been done inappropriately. Consequently, empty city regions have filled in as spots to arrange those squanders, causing visual contamination, populace development and spread of bug disease. The qualities acquired during the assembling system of concrete shows that really the concrete assembling process adds to damage to

the climate where it is featured the nursery impact, brought about by consuming petroleum products, contamination by weighty metals because of mining exercises and exhaust cloud brought about by discharges of particulate matter. Nonetheless, it is critical to consider that this material is fundamental for the extension of improvement. In this way, the ecological effects must be limited by natural proficient cycles, materials reusing, barometrical emanating treatment and furthermore the recuperation of ravaged mining regions, with reforestation. (Mbohwa et al., 2008) in their thorough investigation of the Life Cycle Assessment of the Cement industry in Zimbabwe asses that cement production process gets going with unrefined substance and procurement. Limestone is mined in a quarry where explosives, boring machines, smashers and shipping dump trucks. At the plant, Limestone (75%-80%), Silica <23%, Iron metal <5% and Alumina <5% are blended and squashed, stacked and stored prepared for use. Goedkoop, Metal. Conducted a study on impacts on cement on the environment and health in2008.This study utilized SimaPro Version 7.0 for the examination of the outcomes. The portrayal results show that the significant classifications in the concrete business are respiratory organics and inorganics, environmental change, fermentation/eutrophication and the utilization of non-renewable energy sources.

Abiotic asset exhaustion incorporated the utilization of fuel used in the conveyance of crude dinner and utilization of limestone and earth during readiness of crude feast. Energy exhaustion is chiefly from power and coal utilized during the concrete creation processes. Outflow from energy creation and use adds to an Earth-wide temperature boost especially from carbon dioxide. The concrete furnace dust created is destructive to people and causes respiratory issues and illnesses. Dust from the coal factory and the crude feast storehouses are similarly at risk. The concrete furnace dust is additionally unsafe to plants. When it chooses the leaves, it denies them of photosynthesis. Spillage from the concrete plant, the oven and from the crude factory and crude plant storehouses cover the land and when it comes into contact with water solidifies, forestalling vegetation and upsetting the biological system. Unpredictable natural combinations, nitrogen oxides from diesel vehicles transporting crude feast, and concrete production all contribute to the summertime brown haze. Sulfur oxides and particulate particles (dust) from fuels like diesel and coal used for heating the furnace can cause winter brown haze. The water for cooling the factories is defiled by oils and spills are normal sullyng the water frameworks. The fermentation of amphibians is brought on by the pro fluent from the plant, which is discharged into seagoing bodies and mostly consists of nitrate and sulphate chemicals. Additionally, the delivery of raw food to the oven and the burning of coal in the furnace emit nitrogen and Sulphur oxides, which cause air fermentation. Because of the concentrations of phosphate and nitrate increases in the issuing cooling water, it also contributes to eutrophication (Akada et al., 2023).

Commotion is created by the weighty diesel trucks that convey unrefined substances and items, by the concrete plant during get done with crushing, by the crude factory during crude crushing and by the furnace during pyro handling of crude feast to deliver clinker. A great deal of commotion is likewise created during the mixing of crude feast. The bulk of the respiratory inorganics and the production of concrete are found to be contributed by clinkering. The ecological consequences of eutrophication and fermentation are regulated by respiratory inorganics. Utilizing petroleum-based goods has additional significant implications that contribute to environmental change (Pramanik et al., 2023).

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was carried out in a larger industrial zone called Hattar Industrial Estate in the district of Haripur, which is located in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's Hazara region, which is in the northeastern part of the country.

3.1 System Boundary of the Study

The life cycle model of cement industry shall be represented industrial activates, for the assessment of environmental impacts this study shall follow Gate to Gate LCA approach (See, Figure 1).

- **Functional Unit:**

For LCA & water footprint analysis of cement industries, functional unit can be taken as 1 cement bag of 50 Kg. The raw materials used in cement manufacturing process are limestone 740T/hr, clay 200T/hr, literate 3T/hr and slate 7T/hr .

Figure 1: Life Cycle Model of Cement Industry

Source: Author's adapted from the literature review.

- **Tools:**

Data necessary for the study was collected through primary source. Peer reviewed literature and internal record of the mills was used to gain information regarding all the key stages of system process of cement production as well as details about production capacity of cement mills, electricity usage during whole milling process, fossil fuels consumption (i.e. stationary and mobile sources), transportation of products inside the mill and amount of waste generated by all of these processes. Other tools used were:

1. Questionnaire Development
2. Industrial visit & Data collection
3. Data analysis through SemaPro v9.02 software
4. Digital camera for taking onsite photos.

3.2 Life Cycle Impact Assessment

For the following effects' life cycle inventory data were processed using SimaPro software version 9.2: (AD), (GWP), (OLD), (EP), (MAE), (TE), (FAE) & (HT).

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The LCI data for one cement bag production by cement industries in Hattar Industrial estate during 2021-2022 are presented in Figure 2 and 3. The life cycle impact analysis for one cement bag production and the comparative contribution made by each step in the process to the various environmental effects are shown. Among the other materials limestone and clay contributed most to major impact categories.

Figure 2: Relative proportion of each process's impact on environmental parameters

Figure 3: Relative proportion of each process's impact on environmental parameters

Most of the impacts were induced by that of the cement manufacturing process that takes place on site in AD, limestone has the highest contribution of (68%) and clay has (32%). The relative proportion of acidification potential and eutrophication potential are shown in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4: Relative Proportion of Acidification Potential

Figure 5: Relative Proportion of Eutrophication Potential

In AP the highest impact contributor is limestone (85%) and clay has (15%). Production of one cement bag contributes to eutrophication potential in such a way, that limestone (85%) and Clay contributes (15%) to the eutrophication potential. Global warming and ozone layer depletion are global problems now and production of one bag of cement contributes in global warming as limestone (70%) and Clay (30%) (See, Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6: Relative Proportion of Global Warming Potential)

Figure 7: Relative Proportion of Ozone Layer Depletion

Ozone layer depletion directly results in increase of global warming. Industrial processes of cement manufacture results in ozone layer depletion, limestone has the highest contribution of (66%) and clay (34%). The relative proportion of photochemical oxidation and human toxicity are shown in Figures 8 and 9.

Figure 8: Relative Proportion of Photochemical Oxidation

Production of one cement bag contributes to photochemical oxidation in such a way, that limestone (78%) and Clay contributes (22%) to the photochemical oxidation.

Figure 9: Relative Proportion of Human Toxicity

Skin borne diseases are far most common in today's world. Industrial processes of cement manufacture results in human toxicity, limestone has the highest contribution of (75%), and Clay (25%). In fresh water eco toxicity highest contribution is of limestone (76%) and clay (24%) as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Relative Proportion of Fresh Water Aquatic Ecotox

Figure 11: Relative Proportion of Marine Aquatic Ecotoxicity

The onsite industrial process of the cement manufacture was accountable for most of the impacts in marine aquatic eco toxicity, limestone has the highest contribution of (74%) and Clay (26%), as shown in Figure 11. In terrestrial toxicity highest contribution is of limestone (72%) and clay (28%) as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Relative Proportion of Terrestrial Ecotoxicity

4.1 Emission Inventory to Air, Soil and Water for 1 Cement bag of 50 kg.

Results of the hazardous material emissions inventories for the 50 kg cement bags produced at the cement industry Hattar industrial estate in 2021–2022, as shown in Tables 1 to 3. Most the emissions were from slate (used as raw material). Amongst other materials limestone, clay, literate and slate made the largest influence in the most of the impact categories. The substances which contributed much to air emissions were 1-Propanol (982.5759 μg) followed by Cadmium (733.6822 μg), 2-Methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid (694.6762 pg), Ammonia(475.9006 mg), Chlorpyrifos (465.2295 ng), 2,4-D, dimethylamine salt (343.0878pg), and 1-Butanol(194.2572ng). While substances which largely contributed to water were 2,4-D ester (471.1595pg) followed by Oils, unspecified (515.1826mg), 1,4-Butanediol (415.9003ng), Radium-224 (407.9585 mBq), 1,3-Dioxolan-2-one (358.2829 μg) and 2-Butene, 2-methyl-(211.2441pg). The components that were mostly responsible for soil emission were Benfluralin (845.2131ng) followed by Maneb (843.4606pg), Alachlor (829.8357ng), Fenamiphos (689.4214ng), Diazinon (504.3545ng) and Acetamide (461.9694ng).

Table1: Emission inventory to water for one cement bag of cement produced at Hattar industrial estate Haripur during 2021-2022

Substance	Compartment	Unit	107.5210453
1-Butanol	Water	μg	107.521
1-Pentanol	Water	Ng	107.521
1-Pentene	Water	Ng	107.521
1-Propanol	Water	Ng	107.521
1,3-Dioxolan-2-one	Water	μg	107.521
1,4-Butanediol	Water	Ng	107.521
2-Aminopropanol	Water	Ng	107.521
2-Butene, 2-methyl-	Water	Pg	107.521
2-Chlorobenzaldehyde	Water	Ng	107.521
2-Methyl-1-propanol	Water	Ng	107.521
2-Methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid	Water	Ng	107.521
2-Propanol	Water	μg	107.521
2,4-D ester	Water	Pg	107.521
2,4-D, dimethylamine salt	Water	Ng	107.521
4-Methyl-2-pentanol	Water	Ng	107.521
Acenaphthene	Water	μg	107.521
Acenaphthylene	Water	Ng	107.521

Substance	Compartment	Unit	107.5210453
Acetaldehyde	Water	Mg	107.521
Acetic acid	Water	µg	107.521
Acetone	Water	µg	107.521
Acetonitrile	Water	Ng	107.521
Acetyl chloride	Water	Ng	107.521
Acidity, unspecified	Water	µg	107.521
Metolachlor	Water	Ng	107.521
Molybdenum	Water	Mg	107.521
Monobutyltin	Water	Pg	107.521
Monoethanolamine	Water	Ng	107.521
Monophenyltin	Water	Pg	107.521
Nickel	Water	Mg	107.521
Nitrogen, atmospheric	Water	Mg	107.521
o-Xylene	Water	µg	2.132991
Oils, biogenic	Water	µg	71.86705
Oils, unspecified	Water	Mg	515.1826
Paraffins	Water	µg	11.27817
Pentane	Water	Ng	5.599658
Phenol	Water	Mg	1.585051
Phosphorus	Water	Mg	22.12828

Table 2: Emission inventory to soil for one cement bag of cement produced at Hattar industrial estate Haripur during 2021-2022

Substance	Compartment	Unit	Total
2,4-D	Soil	µg	70.54099
2,4-D ester	Soil	ng	18.40188
2,4-D, dimethylamine salt	Soil	ng	68.43064
Abamectin	Soil	ng	10.81142
Acephate	Soil	µg	2.98729
Acetamide	Soil	ng	461.9694
Alachlor	Soil	ng	829.8357
Aluminium	Soil	mg	103.2254
Barium	Soil	mg	2.75978
Benfluralin	Soil	ng	845.2131
Bensulfuron methyl ester	Soil	pg	145.4563
Benzene, pentachloronitro-	Soil	ng	35.9623
BifenoX	Soil	ng	21.19208
Bifenthrin	Soil	ng	17.30094
Cadmium	Soil	µg	29.68601
Calcium	Soil	mg	338.293
Captan	Soil	µg	24.07738
Carbaryl	Soil	ng	2.215543
Carbendazim	Soil	µg	1.289603
Carbetamide	Soil	µg	1.405403
Carbofuran	Soil	µg	25.2118

Deltamethrin	Soil	ng	3.182752
Desmedipham	Soil	ng	44.74178
Diazinon	Soil	ng	504.3545
Dicamba	Soil	ng	249.8285
Dichlorprop	Soil	ng	20.4045
Epoxiconazole	Soil	ng	51.72701
Esfenvalerate	Soil	ng	2.633271
Ethalfuralin	Soil	ng	24.53516
Ethephon	Soil	µg	1.453203
Ethofumesate	Soil	µg	1.560726
Ethoprop	Soil	ng	33.12475
Fenamiphos	Soil	ng	689.4214
Fenbuconazole	Soil	ng	5.422356
Imazethapyr	Soil	ng	28.04312
Imidacloprid	Soil	µg	3.716032

Table 3: Emission inventory to air for one cement bag of cement produced at Hattar industrial estate Haripur during 2021-2022

Substance	Compartment	Unit	Total
1-Butanol	Air	ng	194.2572
1-Pentanol	Air	ng	16.74017
1-Pentene	Air	ng	174.3118
1-Propanol	Air	µg	982.5759
1,4-Butanediol	Air	ng	187.3257
2-Aminopropanol	Air	ng	5.797338
2-Butene, 2-methyl-	Air	pg	88.01706
2-Methyl-1-propanol	Air	ng	30.10603
2-Methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid	Air	pg	694.6762
2-Nitrobenzoic acid	Air	ng	4.280639
2-Propanol	Air	mg	29.77341
2,4-D ester	Air	ng	4.005279
2,4-D, dimethylamine salt	Air	pg	343.0878
4-Methyl-2-pentanone	Air	µg	16.03831
Acenaphthene	Air	µg	1.21879
Acenaphthylene	Air	ng	24.35076
Acephate	Air	ng	101.7147
Acetaldehyde	Air	mg	4.806656
Acetamide	Air	ng	25.03867
Acetic acid	Air	mg	4.0077
Acetone	Air	mg	1.21074
Acetonitrile	Air	µg	29.12107
Aerosols, radioactive, unspecified	Air	mBq	29.63001
Alachlor	Air	ng	98.8119
Aluminium	Air	g	1.111615
Amine oxide	Air	ng	83.70662
Ammonia	Air	mg	475.9006

Substance	Compartment	Unit	Total
Ammonium carbonate	Air	µg	20.6634
Barium	Air	mg	2.939787
Bentazone	Air	ng	43.25803
Benzal chloride	Air	ng	11.54244
Benzene	Air	mg	27.8062
Benzene, 1-methyl-2-nitro-	Air	ng	3.696411
Benzene, 1,2-dichloro-	Air	ng	54.62335
Cadmium	Air	µg	733.6822
Calcium	Air	mg	114.1232
Carbaryl	Air	ng	11.82897

4.2 Specification Per Substance to Various Environmental Impact

Specification per substance results of harmful components to various environmental impacts of one cement bag of cement produced at Hattar Industrial estate Haripur, as given in Tables 4 to 12. Slate was the major source of emissions (used as raw material). Limestone, clay, literate, and slate, among other materials, contributed the greatest contributions to the majority of the impact categories. Cadmium (0.0012 kg Sbeq), Lead (0.0008 kg Sbeq), Chromium (2.99E-06 kg Sbeq), and Krypton were the main contributors to abiotic depletion (6.12E-07 kg Sbeq). Sulfur dioxide (0.013646 kg Sbeq), nitrogen oxides (0.004984 kg Sbeq), ammonia (0.000761 kg Sbeq), and nitrogen monoxide were the main contributors to acidification potential (1.39E-08 kg Sbeq). Phosphate (0.0048 kg PO₄--- eq), Nitrogen oxides (0.001296 kg PO₄--- eq), Nitrate (0.000539 kg PO₄--- eq), and Ammonia were the main contributors to eutrophication potential (0.000167 kg PO₄--- eq). The substances which largely contributed to global warming potential were Carbon dioxide, fossil (2.307957 kg CO₂ eq), Methane, fossil (0.092063 kg CO₂ eq), Sulfur hexafluoride (0.002938 kg CO₂ eq) and Chloroform (9.6E-07kg CO₂ eq).

The main contributors to the ozone layer depletion potential were bromotrifluoro-methane (Halon 1301) (1.04E-07 kg CFC-11 eq), 1,2-dichloro-1,1,2,2-tetrafluoro-methane (CFC-114; 1.67E-08 kg CFC-11 eq), dichlorodifluoro-methane (CFC-12; 5.97E-09 kg CFC-11 (6E-10 kg CFC-11 eq). Biogenic carbon monoxide (0.000165 kg C₂H₄ eq), formaldehyde (2.08 E-05 kg C₂H₄ eq), ethene (7.08 E-06 kg C₂H₄ eq), and 2-propanol were the chemicals that contributed to photochemical oxidation (5.6E-06 kg C₂H₄ eq). Chromium VI (1.703796kg 1,4-DB eq), Cadmium (0.1063841,4-DB eq), Cobalt (0.114671,4-DB eq), and Carbon disulfide were the chemicals that contributed to human toxicity (5.56E-081,4-DB eq). Barium (0.0196 kg 1,4-DB eq), Copper (0.001857 kg 1,4-DB eq), Lead (0.000435 kg 1,4-DB eq), and Cobalt have been the largest contributors to the fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity (5.62E-05 kg 1,4-DB eq). These elements—Cobalt (268.7793 kg 1,4-DB eq), Copper (121.8217 kg 1,4-DB eq), Barium (2.293034 kg 1,4-DB eq), and Arsenic—were major contributors to marine aquatic ecotoxicity (0.732583 kg 1,4-DB eq). In particular, arsenic (0.0051058 kg 1,4-DB eq), cobalt (7.14203E-05 kg 1,4-DB eq), cadmium (5.9575E-05 kg 1,4-DB eq), and barium (0.0051058 kg 1,4-DB eq) were harmful to terrestrial ecosystems (1.42874E-05 kg 1,4-DB eq).

Table 4: Specification per substance to Abiotic depletion

No	Substance	Compartment	Unit	Total
	Total of all compartments		kg Sbeq	0.017043
6	Cadmium	Raw	kg Sbeq	0.001249
54	Lead	Raw	kg Sbeq	0.000851
9	Chromium	Raw	kg Sbeq	2.99E-06
52	Krypton	Raw	kg Sbeq	6.12E-07
16	Copper, 0.52% in sulfide, Cu 0.27% and Mo 8.2E-3% in crude ore	Raw	kg Sbeq	5.79E-07
47	Indium	Raw	kg Sbeq	5.7E-07
17	Copper, 0.59% in sulfide, Cu 0.22% and Mo 8.2E-3% in crude ore	Raw	kg Sbeq	4.17E-07
46	Gypsum	Raw	kg Sbeq	8.81E-08
3	Barite	Raw	kg Sbeq	4.07E-08
58	Manganese	Raw	kg Sbeq	1.64E-08
75	Phosphorus, 18% in apatite, 4% in	Raw	kg Sbeq	7.83E-09

No	Substance	Compartment	Unit	Total
	crude ore			
4	Borax	Raw	kg Sbeq	5.29E-09
30	Fluorine	Raw	kg Sbeq	6.86E-11
1	Aluminium	Raw	kg Sbeq	1.97E-11
2	Anhydrite	Raw	kg Sbeq	4.82E-12
14	Cobalt	Raw	kg Sbeq	6.61E-13
28	Dolomite	Raw	kg Sbeq	2.07E-13
29	Europium	Raw	kg Sbeq	2.27E-15

Table 5: Specification per substance to Acidification potential

No.	Total of all compartments		kg SO2 eq	0.019391
4	Sulfur dioxide	Air	kg SO2 eq	0.013646
3	Nitrogen oxides	Air	kg SO2 eq	0.004984
1	Ammonia	Air	kg SO2 eq	0.000761
2	Nitrogen monoxide	Air	kg SO2 eq	1.39E-08

Table 6: Specification per substance to Eutrophication Potential

No.	Total of all compartments		kg PO4--- eq	0.00757
11	Phosphate	Water	kg PO4--- eq	0.004869
10	Nitrogen oxides	Air	kg PO4--- eq	0.001296
4	COD, Chemical Oxygen Demand	Water	kg PO4--- eq	0.000561
6	Nitrate	Water	kg PO4--- eq	0.000539
1	Ammonia	Air	kg PO4--- eq	0.000167
15	Phosphorus	Water	kg PO4--- eq	6.77E-05
16	Phosphorus	Soil	kg PO4--- eq	3.54E-05
3	Ammonium, ion	Water	kg PO4--- eq	3.06E-05
14	Phosphorus	Air	kg PO4--- eq	4.04E-06
8	Nitrite	Water	kg PO4--- eq	4.69E-07
5	Nitrate	Air	kg PO4--- eq	4.1E-07
7	Nitrate	Soil	kg PO4--- eq	1.68E-08
9	Nitrogen monoxide	Air	kg PO4--- eq	3.66E-09
2	Ammonium carbonate	Air	kg PO4--- eq	2.48E-09
13	Phosphoric acid	Water	kg PO4--- eq	5.17E-11
12	Phosphoric acid	Air	kg PO4--- eq	1.79E-13

Table 7: Specification per substance to Global warming

No.	Total of all compartments		kg CO2 eq	2.467234
1	Carbon dioxide, fossil	Air	kg CO2 eq	2.307957
22	Methane, fossil	Air	kg CO2 eq	0.092063
14	Methane, biogenic	Air	kg CO2 eq	0.007652
28	Sulfur hexafluoride	Air	kg CO2 eq	0.002938
25	Methane, tetrafluoro-, CFC-14	Air	kg CO2 eq	0.000884
12	Ethane, hexafluoro-, HFC-116	Air	kg CO2 eq	0.000135
18	Methane, chlorodifluoro-, HCFC-22	Air	kg CO2 eq	8.9E-05
20	Methane, dichlorodifluoro-, CFC-12	Air	kg CO2 eq	7.72E-05
	Methane, bromotrifluoro-, Halon			
17	1301	Air	kg CO2 eq	6E-05
24	Methane, tetrachloro-, CFC-10	Air	kg CO2 eq	5.63E-05
27	Methane, trifluoro-, HFC-23	Air	kg CO2 eq	4.31E-05
6	Ethane, 1,1-difluoro-, HFC-152a	Air	kg CO2 eq	5.36E-06
	Methane, bromochlorodifluoro-,			
16	Halon 1211	Air	kg CO2 eq	4.38E-06
4	Chloroform	Air	kg CO2 eq	9.6E-07
13	Methane	Air	kg CO2 eq	6.78E-07
23	Methane, monochloro-, R-40	Air	kg CO2 eq	4.8E-07
19	Methane, dichloro-, HCC-30	Air	kg CO2 eq	2.13E-07
26	Methane, trichlorofluoro-, CFC-11	Air	kg CO2 eq	5.56E-08
21	Methane, dichlorofluoro-, HCFC-21	Air	kg CO2 eq	2.37E-09
15	Methane, bromo-, Halon 1001	Air	kg CO2 eq	1.04E-10

Table 8: Specification per substance to Ozone layer depletion

	Total of all compartments		kg CFC-11 eq	1.85E-07
	Methane, bromotrifluoro-, Halon			
7	1301	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	1.04E-07
11	Methane, tetrachloro-, CFC-10	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	3.75E-08
	Methane, bromochlorodifluoro-,			
6	Halon 1211	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	1.72E-08
	Ethane, 1,2-dichloro-1,1,2,2-			
3	tetrafluoro-, CFC-114	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	1.67E-08
9	Methane, dichlorodifluoro-, CFC-12	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	5.97E-09
8	Methane, chlorodifluoro-, HCFC-22	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	1.78E-09
	Ethane, 1,1,2-trichloro-1,2,2-			
2	trifluoro-, CFC-113	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	6.55E-10
10	Methane, monochloro-, R-40	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	6E-10
1	Ethane, 1,1,1-trichloro-, HCFC-140	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	1.19E-10
5	Methane, bromo-, Halon 1001	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	7.68E-12
	Ethane, 2-chloro-1,1,1,2-tetrafluoro-,			
4	HCFC-124	Air	kg CFC-11 eq	3.87E-12

Table 9: Specification per substance to Human toxicity

No	Substance	Compartment	Unit	Total
71	Chromium VI	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.703796
52	Cadmium	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.106384
31	Barium	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.054608
23	Arsenic	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.040048
74	Cobalt	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.011467
38	Benzene	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.00715
30	Barium	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.002222
70	Chromium	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.001242
126	Mercury	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.001057
61	Carbon disulfide	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.000393
16	Ammonia	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.76E-05
96	Ethene	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.51E-06
62	Carbon disulfide	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	5.56E-08
131	Methane, bromo-, Halon 1001	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	7.29E-09
86	Dichromate	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	6.04E-09
39	Benzene, 1,2-dichloro-	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.95E-10
85	Dichlorprop	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	9.22E-11
2	2-Methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.45E-11
1	2-Methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.02E-11

Table 10: Specification per substance to Terrestrial ecotoxicity

21	Arsenic	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.005105883
82	Cobalt	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	7.14203E-05
59	Cadmium	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	5.9575E-05
85	Copper	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	5.84608E-05
23	Arsenic	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	5.52086E-05
31	Barium	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.7515E-05
29	Barium	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.42874E-05
84	Cobalt	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	7.33262E-06
61	Cadmium	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.95756E-06
68	Carbon disulfide	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	8.37619E-07
62	Captan	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	9.87173E-10
36	Benzene	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.33777E-10
39	Benzene, 1,2-dichloro-	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	3.73984E-10
69	Carbon disulfide	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.10033E-10
37	Benzene	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	5.35352E-11
1	2-Methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.97321E-14
38	Benzene, 1,2-dichloro-	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.88958E-14
22	Arsenic	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.37972E-22
83	Cobalt	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.65072E-22
30	Barium	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.40373E-23
60	Cadmium	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.02701E-25

Table 11: Specification per substance to Fresh water aquatic Eco toxicity

No	Substance	Compartment	Unit	Total
	Total of all compartments		kg 1,4-DB eq	2.205514
30	Barium	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.019659
85	Copper	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.001857
128	Lead	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.000435
29	Barium	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.000126
122	Hydrogen fluoride	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.00011
84	Cobalt	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	5.62E-05
127	Lead	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	3.5E-05
68	Carbon disulfide	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	5.38E-06
69	Carbon disulfide	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.4E-06
37	Benzene	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	3.56E-07
36	Benzene	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.33E-09
35	Bentazone	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.21E-09
70	Chlorfenvinphos	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	8.47E-10
2	2-Methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.41E-11
71	Chloridazon	Soil	kg 1,4-DB eq	3.23E-11
73	Chloroform	Water	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.89E-12
72	Chloroform	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	3.05E-12
1	2-Methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid	Air	kg 1,4-DB eq	7.36E-13

Table 12: Specification per substance to Photochemical Oxidation

No	Substance	Compartment	Unit	Total
	Total of all compartments		kg C2H4 eq	0.001004
16	Carbon monoxide, biogenic	Air	kg C2H4 eq	0.000165
31	Formaldehyde	Air	kg C2H4 eq	2.08E-05
26	Ethene	Air	kg C2H4 eq	7.08E-06
33	Heptane	Air	kg C2H4 eq	6.93E-06
6	2-Propanol	Air	kg C2H4 eq	5.6E-06
15	Butane	Air	kg C2H4 eq	5.34E-06
23	Ethane	Air	kg C2H4 eq	4.15E-06
51	Propane	Air	kg C2H4 eq	3.31E-06
8	Acetaldehyde	Air	kg C2H4 eq	3.08E-06
25	Ethanol	Air	kg C2H4 eq	2.76E-07
50	Propanal	Air	kg C2H4 eq	2.1E-07
10	Acetone	Air	kg C2H4 eq	1.14E-07
32	Formic acid	Air	kg C2H4 eq	5.71E-09
22	Dimethyl carbonate	Air	kg C2H4 eq	8.7E-10
2	1-Pentene	Air	kg C2H4 eq	1.7E-10
1	1-Butanol	Air	kg C2H4 eq	1.2E-10
	2-Methyl-1-propanol	Air	kg C2H4 eq	1.08E-11
4	2-Butene, 2-methyl-	Air	kg C2H4 eq	7.41E-14

4.3 Discussion

This research employed the life cycle assessment (LCA) method. The hotspot sources which causes health issues for one cement bag produced by cement industries in Hattar Industrial estate Haripur during 2021-2022 were Slate, limestone, laterite and clay. Silicosis is a risk associated with slate industry, which is growing right now, which implies more workers as well. There is a danger of pneumoconiosis and other respiratory problems in the slate sector.(Rego et al., 2001). Although advanced technologies have made it feasible to lessen the related environmental impacts, carbonate rock resources like limestone cannot be extracted through quarrying or mining activities without producing some environmental problems. Due to habitat loss, dust, noise, vibrations, erosion, subsidence, and sedimentation, mining activities alter the geomorphology and land-use patterns. Furthermore, changes in groundwater quality, flow, and overall water quality are brought on by limestone mining (Ganapathi & Phukan, 2020).High noise levels are caused when equipment like excavator is being used, as well as during drilling, blasting, loading, and unloading operations. Both people and the wildlife existing in the mine lease area may be impacted by the cumulative effect of all the noise made at the mining site (Faroz Ahmad et al., 2014).When inhaled over an extended length of time, minerals in clay can be found to have a negative impact on human health. Often their toxicity is connected to the presence of quartz or asbestos from mining operations, clay minerals can cause a range of disorders in the lung, including cancer, mesothelioma, and pneumoconiosis (Carretero et al., 2006). It is widely believed that laterite, a kind of soil and rock rich in iron and aluminum, originated in hot, humid tropical regions. Due to its high iron oxide concentration, nearly are all laterites rusty-red in color (Satpudke & Prashantashutkar, 2016).During the process, iron oxides are emitted, which produces metal fume illness, a flu-like condition that is characterized by a metallic taste, fever, chills, pains, chest tightness, and coughing. Pneumoconiosis with coughing, shortness of breath, and alterations on a chest x-ray can be brought on by constant exposure to iron oxide fumes.

4.4 Sensitivity analysis for the clean and green options in Cement production

Change in environmental impact due to variations of input can be carried out via sensitivity analysis. Determination of the degree to which change in inputs influences the final output results, this trend of analyzing the change in final results caused by variation of inputs is known as sensitivity analysis. Top most hotspots which influence the environment during production of cement at Hattar industrial estate are summarized in Fig1. Optimizing the mix to utilize the available raw materials as efficiently as possible is the main goal of using alternative resources. Although a variety of calcareous raw materials can be used to make cement, the most common ones are limestone, chalk, or marble. Most of the time, there aren't enough substantial deposits or volumes of other calcium-bearing sources to be employed as substitutes. Due to its accessibility and affordability, clay/mudstone is the primary source of silica, alumina, and iron oxides. However, mudstone frequently lacks the proper chemical balance of elements, necessitating the need of external additions. These could include bauxite, fly ash (also known as pulverized fuel ash PFA), silica sand, and iron oxides. PFA contains fewer alkalis and a higher alumina to silica ratio than the majority of mudstones. Blended cements are being produced in greater quantity. These might include a percentage of PFA, either alone or in combination (a by-product of coal-fired power stations). Limestone has historically been the primary raw material used in cement manufacture. Although limestone is widely available, its conversion into lime, or "decarbonation," is responsible for more than 60% of the industry's CO₂ emissions. In place of natural materials like clay, shale, and limestone, selected waste and byproducts containing beneficial elements like calcium, silica, alumina, and iron can be used as raw materials in the kiln.

Some waste products contain valuable minerals and can be used to produce energy. For instance, sewage sludge produces ash, which is utilized as a raw material to create clinker, despite having a low but significant calorific value. The manufacturing of cement may be able to offer a solution by substituting crushed or otherwise processed concrete for limestone. In place of "virgin" limestone, materials such as blast furnace slag, concrete crusher sand, aerated concrete meal, and fractions from demolition waste that have already undergone decarburization could be used. This would prevent the release of CO₂ during the process of turning the materials into lime. Using sewage sludge as an alternative to limestone and pulverized fuel ash as an alternative to clay used during the manufacturing process of cement produced at Hattar industrial estate, the final results differ as; substituting clay with PFA leads to decrease of 5% in its impact on abiotic depletion, as of substituting of limestone with sewage sludge results in decrease of 13% in its impact on abiotic depletion. Substituting clay with PFA leads to decrease of 2% in its impact on acidification, as of substituting limestone with sewage sludge results in decrease of 17% in its impact on acidification. Substituting clay with PFA leads to decrease of 5% in its impact on eutrophication, as of substituting limestone with sewage sludge decrease of 19% in its impact on eutrophication. Substituting clay with PFA leads to decrease of 3% in its impact on global warming potential, as of substituting limestone with sewage sludge decrease of 14% in its impact on global warming potential. Substituting clay with PFA leads to decrease of 3% in its impact on human toxicity, as of substituting limestone with sewage sludge decrease of 15% in its impact on human toxicity. Substituting clay with PFA leads to decrease of 2% in its impact on freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity, as of substituting limestone with sewage sludge decrease of 15% in its impact on freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity. Substituting clay with PFA leads to decrease 3% in its impact on

marine water ecotoxicity, as of substituting limestone with sewage sludge decrease of 15% in its impact on marine water ecotoxicity. As of in case of terrestrial ecotoxicity substituting limestone with sewage sludge leads to the decrease of about 17% and in photochemical oxidation as of substituting limestone with sewage sludge leads to the decrease of 50% in their impacts on environment (see, Figure 13).

Figure 13: Sensitivity Analysis

With the rise of consumerism and urbanization in developing nation, different environmental issues have risen for countries like Pakistan, one of the major concerning issues for the country is to manage the waste generation from industrial activities and their impacts on biotic and abiotic factors and the proper management and control, rapid industrialization and urbanization in many countries. Organizations actually need to incorporate waste management and prevention methods into their industrial processes due to growing environmental concerns related to industrial waste (Bennett, 1994). Any measure that avoids or decreases the emission of pollutants or waste at their source, which may result from inefficient industrial processes, poor operating procedures, or badly built or used equipment, is referred to as pollution prevention (Freeman & Harris, 1995; Shen et al., 2004). Implementing a pollution prevention effort is a business strategy that may provide an organization a number of significant benefits (Abou-Elela & Zaher, 1998 a).

The organization may lower its expenses related with waste disposal, increasing employee safety, and lower long-term liability by reducing the quantity of waste produced or discharged. Furthermore, pollution preventative measures may improve the efficiency of the production line and save costs related to the purchase of materials, inventory management, and other expenses. Any subsequent adjustments to productivity or spending may aid the business in preserving or enhancing its competitiveness in the market (Abou-Elela & Zaher, 1998 b). The studies show that there are various pollution prevention strategies that could be employed with significant financial benefits for the industry as well as a reduction in environmental pollution. These alternatives include anything from simple, low-cost changes to housekeeping procedures to cost reductions that may be achieved through the recovery of process chemicals and prospective products from waste materials.

The industry's management is accountable for maintenance and conservation of the green spaces within and surrounding the business. The cement industry must be committed to understanding the effects of its output. Since raw materials like limestone, clay, literate, and slate are required to create cement, among other things, it must develop ways to reduce those elements that have an impact on the environment from resource inputs and outputs. Primary materials for cement had the greatest impacts on the majority of environmental impact categories, including limestone, clay, slate, and literate, even though they had a significant impact on abiotic depletion, global warming, eutrophication potential, photochemical oxidation, and ozone layer.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A gate-to-gate lifecycle analysis of cement produced at Pakistan's Hattar Industrial Estate is presented in this research. Cement manufacturing industry production-weighted average statistics were used to create life cycle inventory data in KP, Pakistan. Secondary data were obtained from scholarly publications that had been examined and published. The research examines how the use of raw materials like limestone, clay, slate, and literate has an adverse impact on the surrounding. Ten environmental impact categories are used to pinpoint the key hotspots and characterize the production process. Primary materials such as limestone, clay, literate, and slate for cement, significantly contributed to abiotic depletion, global warming, eutrophication potential, photochemical oxidation, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, and marine aquatic ecotoxicity impacts. The majority of the environmental impact categories had the greatest influence from the materials mentioned above.

The research shows that there are several pollution prevention techniques that could be employed which can offer considerable financial benefits for the business as well as a reduction in environmental pollution. These possibilities vary from straightforward, low-cost adjustments to housekeeping practices to possible cost reductions from recovering process chemicals and prospective products from waste materials.

The study's primary goal was to assess the environmental impacts of cement manufacturing process, and to give some solutions\ suggestions to minimize its impacts on environment during manufacturing process of cement. The industry's administration is liable to upkeep and maintain the green spaces within and around the industry. The cement industry must be dedicated to recognizing the effects of its output. Therefore, it must find a way to cut back on the elements that have a significant negative influence on the environment. Based on current study findings:

- Air Pollution Control Devices

At first, exhaust gases from cement industries were released into the environment without any reduction process. To reduce gas emissions, later installed bag filters (BF) and electrostatic precipitators were utilized. Modern BFs are utilized to reduce gas emissions since they are highly effective at de-dusting under normal conditions. BFs serve as filters that can be made of woven or felted cotton, synthetic fibers, or glass fiber in the form of tubes or envelopes that let gases through while stopping dust particles that could gather at the bottom.

- Wastewater and Industrial Process Wastewater Treatment

Water is solely utilized to cool production processes in the cement sector. In some activities, process effluent with a high pH and suspended particles may be produced. Water used for cooling purposes is often recycled and utilized again during the process. Utilizing a settling basin and clarifier, screening and reduced suspended solids are accomplished. For the establishment of green belts, water treated at a waste water treatment facility should be used. Additionally, this green belt reduces noise pollution.

- Solid Wastes

The major solid waste products in the manufacture of cement are clinker and rocks that serve as filler taken out of the raw materials during the processing of raw meal. Solid waste also includes fly ash from a power plant and kiln dust. Other waste, such as spent oil and metal scrap, is produced during plant maintenance. Most of the time, these wastes are dumped in landfills outside, which can lead to lung and breathing problems. Lime waste generated by the crushing department may be re-crushed and used to make clinker or treat sulphates. After being gathered from different air pollution control systems, dust is recycled in the manufacturing process.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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